

A Study of Changing Antimicrobial Drug Resistance Pattern in Pediatric Patients at Tertiary Care Hospital of Western Rajasthan

Aditi Arha¹, Rajkumar Rathore², Prabhu Prakash³¹Senior Resident, Department of Pharmacology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Jodhpur²Senior Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Dr SN Medical College, Jodhpur, Rajasthan³Senior Professor, Department of Microbiology, Dr SN Medical College, Jodhpur, Rajasthan

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Aditi Arha

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Children receive antibiotics more frequently since children are frequently victims of ailments of diverse etiology. Growing antimicrobial resistance (AMR) among them necessitates specialized methods for identifying, treating, and preventing resistant infections. Antimicrobial resistance trends in adults and children can vary greatly.

Material and Method: The study is a Retrospective observational study. A total of 587 samples were taken randomly from microbiology laboratory culture and sensitivity during the years 2019, 2020, and 2021 from the pediatric department. Resistance against antimicrobial drugs was recorded from the data received.

Result: Out of 587 samples included in the study, 248 (42.85%) were infected. The number of samples and infectivity gradually increased in subsequent years. Blood and urine samples were the most frequently received samples. 80% of all samples were resistant to ampicillin (AMP) whereas resistance for Vancomycin (VA) was lowest at 4.4%, followed by Linezolid (LZ) at 6.4%.

Conclusion: Antimicrobial drug resistance is a big hurdle for doctors and health care workers, there should be judicious use of antimicrobials in pediatric patients

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance, Pediatric patients, Drug resistance.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Drugs that specifically inhibit the growth of microbes or kill them are known as antimicrobials. They can be chemical substances with natural or synthetic origins. Antimicrobial resistance can result through the unwarranted use of antimicrobial medications. It is more difficult to treat infections brought on by resistant bacteria.

Antibiotic resistance causes increased mortality, longer hospital stays, and higher medical expenses. The way antibiotics are prescribed and used worldwide needs some changes. Antibiotic resistance will continue to pose a serious concern even if new medications are produced in the absence of a change in lifestyle [1].

Since children are frequently victims of ailments of diverse etiology, from the more common urinary tract infections to the less common meningitis, it is known that children receive antibiotics more frequently than any other form of medication. Children are prone to illness, and growing antimicrobial resistance (AMR) among them necessitates specialized methods for identifying, treating, and preventing resistant infections [2].

These include challenges with diagnosis and detecting resistance, a shortage of new antibiotics or formulations suitable for children, and restricted access to research and clinical trials [3]. Antimicrobial resistance trends in adults and children can vary greatly. According to estimates, newborn sepsis caused by bacteria resistant to first-line antibiotics causes the highest infant mortality in India [4].

Therefore, in patients who have an unfavorable course despite receiving adequate antibiotic therapy, antibiotic resistance should be considered [5]. Research efforts in the domain of antibiotic resistance in pediatric illnesses should be significantly increased in light of the growing issue of antibiotic resistance and the significant gaps in our knowledge in this particular area.

Newer last resort antibiotics are well tolerated in patients but there are cases of Linezolid resistance as well as Vancomycin resistance [7] which can be dangerous in upcoming time. In this study, we wanted to analyze the trend of antimicrobial resistance in western Rajasthan as there were not

many studies done in western Rajasthan regarding antimicrobial resistance pattern in the last three years.

Objectives

- To assess and analyze the antimicrobial sensitivity pattern in pediatric patients during the years 2019, 2020, and 2021 at our institute.
- To find changes in the resistance pattern of antimicrobial agents during these three years

Material and Method

Study Location: After taking permission from the institutional ethics committee study was started.

Sample Size: The sample size was calculated at a 95% confidence interval and 5% relative allowable error using the formula for the sample size for estimation of a single sample proportion –

$$N = \frac{(Z_{1-\alpha/2})^2 P (1 - P)}{E^2}$$

$$N = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 84 (100 - 84)}{(4.2)^2}$$

$$N = 292$$

Where, $Z_{1-\alpha/2}$ = Standard normal deviate for 95% confidence interval (taken as 1.96)

P = Expected proportion of samples with Ampicillin resistance (taken as 84% as reported by Erol et al among pediatric patients. Similar prevalence of ampicillin was reported by Hummers et al among gynecology patients.)

E = Relative allowable error (taken as 5% of P)

The sample size was calculated to be 292 subjects and was increased to around 500 as we excluded data with incomplete records. Therefore 500 subjects from the pediatric department constituted our sample size. Our sampling frame included records of all pediatric patients noted in the microbiology lab during the years 2019, 2020, and 2021 and it was stratified into 3 groups according to 2019, 2020, and 2021 year. 500 samples from the above strata were selected by Simple Random Sampling

Study design:

Inclusion criteria: Samples received at the microbiology laboratory for culture sensitivity testing during the years 2019, 2020, and 2021 from the pediatric department.

Exclusion criteria: Samples with incomplete records.

Resistance against antimicrobial drugs was recorded from data received at the microbiology laboratory from the years 2019, 2020, and 2021. Age, sex, patient ID, unit, and type of samples such as blood, urine, or Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF) were recorded, and antimicrobial sensitivity patterns were assessed.

Result

As the number of samples was too large, we randomly selected 5% of samples from each year, 2019, 2020, and 2021. The total number of samples collected and the number of infected samples out of the total samples are shown in Table 1.

A total of 587 samples were included in the study, out of which 248 (42.85%) were infected.

Table 1: Number of samples collected

	2019	2020	2021
Total	159	176	252
Sterile	99	102	138
Infected	60	74	114

From Table 1, we can see that the number of samples in the microbiology lab increased from 2019 to 2020 and from 2020 to 2021. Out of the total samples received, infective samples also increased by 39.62%, 42.05%, and 45.24% in 2019, 2020, and 2021, respectively, which shows infectivity is gradually increasing in the study population. Due to Covid-19, there was a decrease in patient inflow in tertiary care hospital.

Table 2: Type of sample collected. Abbreviations- CSF: Cerebrospinal Fluid, ET tube: Endotracheal tube, KLB: Klebs Loeffler bacilli

Samples	2019	2020	2021
Blood	45	62	85
CSF	2	1	1
Urine	7	4	20
Pus	0	1	3
Throat swab	1	0	0
Ear swab	1	0	0
ET tube	1	2	2
Tracheal aspirate	0	0	1
Pleural Fluid	1	1	1

Stool	1	2	0
KLB staining	0	1	0
Skin scrapping for fungal isolates	1	0	1

We can see in Table 2 that blood and urine samples are the most frequently received samples. Infectivity is increasing following subsequent years, where it doubled in blood samples and tripled in urine samples in 2021 compared to 2019.

Table 3: Type of microorganisms seen in the samples

	Microorganism	2019	2020	2021
Gram-positive Bacteria	CoNS	15	15	0
	CoNS (mrsa)	3	12	2
	S. aureus	9	9	19
	S. aureus (mrsa)	4	5	2
	S. aureus (mssa)	0	3	25
	Enterococcus	5	3	7
	S. viridans	0	1	0
	Beta hemolytic streptococcus	1	0	0
	Other Gpb grown	4	5	7
Gram-negative Bacteria	Acinetobacter	3	5	8
	E. coli	3	4	19
	Klebsiella	5	8	16
	Pseudomonas	3	2	7
	Citrobacter	0	1	2
Fungus	Candida	5	1	0

Abbreviations: CoNS: coagulase-negative staphylococci, MRSA: Methicillin Resistant Staphylococcus Aureus, S. aureus: Staphylococcus Aureus, MSSA: Methicillin Sensitive Staphylococcus Aureus, S. viridans: Streptococcus viridans, Gpb: Gram-Positive Bacteria, E. coli: Escherichia coli

We can see in table 3, that coagulase negative staphylococci (CoNS) was the most common microorganism present in all samples of 2019 and 2020, whereas S. aureus (MSSA), E. coli, S. aureus (MRSA) were predominant in 2021. We analysed the data in which common microorganisms were found and studied their resistance patterns. Out of

all samples, 60 were tested for ampicillin resistance, and found that 80% of all samples were resistant to ampicillin (AMP).

Resistance for Vancomycin (VA) was lowest at 4.4%, followed by Linezolid (LZ) at 6.4% and Piperacillin-tazobactam (PIT) at 17.2%.

Table 4: Antimicrobial resistance pattern in Acinetobacter samples, the number in the bracket with the year represents the number of samples received.

Acinetobacter (Year/ Antibiotic)	AT %	AMC %	CAZ %	CPM %
2019 (3)	66.6	100	-	33.3
2020 (5)	100	-	-	20
2021 (8)	66.6	83.3	80	50

S- Sensitive, R- Resistant, I- Intermediate. Abbreviations- AT: Aztreonam, AMC: Amoxicillin and clavulanic acid, CAZ: Ceftazidime, CPM: Cefepime.

For Acetobacter cases (Table 4), all the samples gradually increased in consecutive cases. Resistance to Cefepime (CPM) gradually increased from 2020 (20%) to 2021 (50%) samples. Out of 6 samples tested for Amoxicillin and clavulanic acid (AMC) 5 were resistant in 2021. CoNS were resistant to ampicillin while sensitive to linezolid and vancomycin.

Table 5: Antimicrobial resistance pattern in E. coli, the number in the bracket with the year represents the number of samples received

E. coli (Year/ Antibiotic)	AT %	AMC %	CAZ %	CPM %	CPZ %
2019 (3)	50	100	0	66.6	100
2020 (4)	75	0	100	50	100
2021 (19)	62.5	85.7	76.9	33.3	80

S- Sensitive, R- Resistant, I-Intermediate. Abbreviations- AT: Aztreonam, AMC: Amoxicillin and clavulanic acid, CAZ: Ceftazidime, CPM: Cefepime, CPZ: Cefoperazone

For E. coli, out of all the samples tested for CPM, 50% of cases were resistant in 2019 and 2010, and in 2021, only 33% of cases were resistant. All the samples in 2019 and 2020 with 80% of cases in 2021 were resistant to Cefoperazone (CPZ). For Gentamycin, out of three samples, two were analysed for sensitivity to it (100%) in 2019, while out of 19 cases, four samples were analysed in 2021, where 50% of cases were resistant.

Table 6: Antimicrobial resistance pattern in Klebsiellas, the number in the bracket with the year represents the number of samples received

Klebsiellas (Year/ Antibiotic)	AT %	AMC %	CAZ %	CPM %	CPZ %	MRP %	PIT %	IPM %
2019 (5)	66.6	50	-	75	66.6	0	0	-
2020 (8)	87.5	100	71.42	37.5	100	0	28.5	0
2021 (16)	70	80	70	71.42	100	0	33	15

S- Sensitive, R- Resistant, I-Intermediate. Abbreviations- AT: Aztreonam, AMC: Amoxicillin and clavulanic acid, CAZ: Ceftazidime, CPM: Cefepime, CPZ: Cefoperazone, MRP: Meropenem, PIT: Piperacillin-tazobactam, IPM: Imipenem

For Klebsiella (Table 6), sensitivity to AMC gradually decreased from 50% in 2019 to 20% in 2021. A mixed pattern was seen for gentamycin. All the samples were sensitive for MRP, while 28.5% of cases were resistant for PIT in 2020 and 33% were resistant in 2021. Out of all the cases tested for IPM, 100% were sensitive in 2020, while 85% were sensitive in 2021, which shows increasing resistance.

Table 7: Antimicrobial resistance pattern in Staphylococcus aureus (S.aureus), the number in the bracket with the year represents the number of samples received

S. Aurous (Year/ Antibiotic)	AMP %	AMC %	CZ %	LZ %	VA %
2019 (9)	100	100	100	0	0
2020 (9)	100	50	62.5	0	33
2021 (19)	100	69.1	76	0	33

S- Sensitive, R- Resistant, I-Intermediate. Abbreviations- AMP: Ampicillin, AMC: Amoxicillin and clavulanic acid, CZ: Cefazolin, LZ: Linezolid, VA: Vancomycin

For S.aureus, all cases were resistant to AMP, while 100% of the samples tested were resistant to AMC in 2019, and 50% of cases were resistant to AMC in 2020 and 2021. Out of 9 cases in 2020, 8 samples were tested for CZ, of which 37.5% were sensitive, and out of 19 samples received in 2021, 17 were tested for CZ, of which 23.5% were sensitive. All the cases were sensitive to linezolid in three years, while for vancomycin, 33% of samples were resistant in 2020 and 2021.

Discussion

Antibiotics are medicines that fight bacterial infections. Antibiotic resistance is becoming an increasingly serious issue. It occurs when bacteria adapt and become resistant to an antibiotic's effects. Bacteria that are resistant might keep expanding and multiplying. Treatment for resistant infections can be challenging and perhaps impossible. Each year, infections brought on by resistance kill millions of people. The treatment of infections brought on by resistant microorganisms is more challenging and frequently involves using higher dosages of antibiotics or more risky alternatives. These methods might also cost more money. In emerging nations like India, the usage of antibiotics is rising daily. It is more difficult to treat infections brought on by resistant bacteria. Antibiotic resistance causes increased mortality, longer hospital stays, and higher medical expenses. Because antibiotics are frequent-

ly used to treat infections like UTIs, antibiotic resistance is frequently observed in female patients. Increased mortality results from an increase in the proportion of resistant newborns and neonates.

Ampicillin was the most resistant medication in our investigation. The prevalence and antibiotic resistance patterns for the six most prevalent uropathogens were examined in a study by Erol B et al., which was a retrospective cross-sectional investigation of bacteria isolated from children between 2009 and 2014. They discovered that between 2009 and 2014, ampicillin had the 70% highest antimicrobial resistance rates in E coli and meropenem had 0.19% [8]. Another study by Gökçe et al. evaluated antibiotic resistance trends in children with UTI between the years 2011 and 2014 and 2001 and 2003. The most common bacteria isolated during all study periods was Escherichia coli. Staphylococcus aureus was the most frequently isolated bacterium in our investigation [9].

Staphylococcus aureus and Klebsiella were found to be the most often reported Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, respectively, in a study conducted by Dharampal D et al in their review, which was consistent with our data. Common Gram-negative pathogens have exceptionally high levels of resistance to ampicillin and gentamicin, and common Gram-negative blood stream isolates had similarly high levels of resistance to

cephalosporins [10]. In a study done by Hummers-Pradier E et al [11] E. coli resistance levels were 40% for amoxicillin, co-amoxiclav, first-generation oral cephalosporins, trimethoprim, and cotrimoxazole. Fluoroquinolone resistance was 9 percent. Nitrofurantoin (2%) and third generation oral cephalosporins (3%), however, continued to have modest E. coli resistance rates. Patients who were complex or older were far more likely to experience resistance.

In a study by Tan et al [12], they found that E. coli was the predominant microorganism and that they had a 72% resistance rate for ampicillin, whereas in our study though E. coli samples were more numerous, all the cases were resistant to ampicillin.

Conclusion

Antimicrobial drug resistance is a big hurdle for the doctors and health care workers, there should be judicious use of antimicrobials in pediatric patients. Every hospital should have antibiotic policy. Prescription auditing should be done on regular basis.

References

- Ventola CL. The Antibiotic Resistance Crisis. *Pharm Ther*. 2015 Apr;40(4):277–83.
- Medernach RL, Logan LK. The Growing Threat of Antibiotic Resistance in Children. *Infect Dis Clin North Am*. 2018 Mar; 32(1):1–17.
- Enane LA, Christenson JC. Global emerging resistance in pediatric infections with TB, HIV, and gram-negative pathogens. *Paediatr Int Child Health*. 2021 Jan 2; 41(1):65–75.
- Laxminarayan R, Matsoso P, Pant S, Brower C, Røttingen JA, Klugman K, et al. Access to effective antimicrobials: a worldwide challenge. *Lancet Lond Engl*. 2016 Jan 9; 387(10014):168–75.
- Romandini A, Pani A, Schenardi PA, Pattarino GAC, De Giacomo C, Scaglione F. Antibiotic Resistance in Pediatric Infections: Global Emerging Threats, Predicting the Near Future. *Antibiotics*. 2021 Apr 6; 10(4):393.
- Markwart R, Willrich N, Eckmanns T, Werner G, Ayobami O. Low Proportion of Linezolid and Daptomycin Resistance Among Blood-borne Vancomycin-Resistant Enterococcus faecium and Methicillin-Resistant Staphylococcus aureus Infections in Europe. *Front Microbiol* [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2023 May 6]; 12. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmicb.2021.664199>
- Selim S. Mechanisms of gram-positive vancomycin resistance (Review). *Biomed Rep*. 2022 Jan; 16(1):7.
- Erol B, Culpun M, Caskurlu H, Sari U, Cag Y, Vahaboglu H, et al. Changes in antimicrobial resistance and demographics of UTIs in pediatric patients in a single institution over a 6-year period. *J Pediatr Urol*. 2018 Apr; 14(2):176.e1-176.e5.
- Gökçe İ, Çiçek N, Güven S, Altuntaş Ü, Bıyıklı N, Yıldız N, et al. Changes in Bacterial Resistance Patterns of Pediatric Urinary Tract Infections and Rationale for Empirical Antibiotic Therapy. *Balk Med J*. 2017 Sep 29; 34(5):432–5.
- Dharmapalan D, Shet A, Yewale V, Sharland M. High Reported Rates of Antimicrobial Resistance in Indian Neonatal and Pediatric Blood Stream Infections. *J Pediatr Infect Dis Soc*. 2017 Sep; 6(3):e62–8.
- Hummers-Pradier E, Koch M, Ohse AM, Heizmann WR, Kochen MM. Antibiotic resistance of urinary pathogens in female general practice patients. *Scand J Infect Dis*. 2005; 37(4):256–61.
- Tan J, Wang Y, Gong X, Li J, Zhong W, Shan L, et al. Antibiotic resistance in neonates in China 2012-2019: A multicenter study. *J Microbiol Immunol Infect Wei Mian Yu Gan Ran Za Zhi*. 2022 Jun; 55(3):454–62.